

Municipal Fiscal Autonomy and Capital Expenditure : A Study of Municipal Corporations in Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

Capital expenditure by the urban local governments is one the key elements that actively builds infrastructure in metropolitan areas and cities of the country. Rapid urbanisation and migration towards cities continue to place more and more strain on civic infrastructure, while limited revenue generation capacities and over dependence of urban local bodies on higher tiers of government limits their ability to keep up with the growing demand for civic amenities in urban areas. This paper empirically tests the impact of municipal fiscal autonomy and local economic growth on capital expenditure incurred by the municipal corporations of Uttar Pradesh. The Random Effects model has been used to account for entity specific effects and small number of observations. Key results obtained in the study indicate, expenditure decentralisation, revenue autonomy, and local economic growth have a significant positive impact on capital expenditure. Whereas, the ability to finance spending through own sourced revenue is negatively associated with capital expenditures. Revenue decentralisation and size of the municipal corporations are insignificant and do not impact the quantum of capital expenditure.

Keywords

Municipal Finance, Urban Development, Fiscal Decentralisation, Local Government Finance, capital investments.

Introduction

The infrastructure and services that are offered determine how far a region may advance. The lack of adequate infrastructure and services in many developing countries negatively affects productivity in cities and towns (Ingram & Kessides, 1994). (Mathur, 2013). Such infrastructure and services are provided by local government institutions, which are important players in the local governance process (Aijaz, 2007). Because local governments are closer to the public and have a better understanding of the needs and preferences of the community, they are ideal for fostering growth and development at the local level (Oates, 1972). The local governments' autonomy in decisions regarding income collection and expenditure has a significant impact on the development of regions and the effectiveness of the public sector (Bird, 1993; Martinez-Vazquez et al., 2017; Rao M Govind, 2002). One of the primary factors accelerating the expansion of infrastructure in metropolitan areas is capital investment by local governments (Hasanuddin et al., 2021a). The primary funding sources for these expenditures include government transfers, non-tax revenue streams, and revenues from local taxes.

In India, an urban area is defined as one where the population density surpasses 400 people per square kilometre (0.62 miles), at least 75% of the working population is employed in non-agricultural activities, and the population exceeds 5000 people[1]. Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) are the local government organisations in India that oversee urban regions. Municipal Corporations, which oversee larger metropolitan areas with a population of over a million, Municipal Councils or Municipalities, which oversee smaller cities with a population of less than a million, and Nagar Panchayats, which oversee towns or cities with a population of up to a lakh, are the three categories into which the ULBs in India are divided[2]. In Uttar Pradesh, there are a total of 17 Municipal Corporations governing a large proportion of the state's total urban population. According to the Census of India (2011), 11.80 per cent of India's urban population resides in Uttar Pradesh and the proportion of urban population to state's total population also increased from 20.78 per cent in 2001 to 22.28 per cent. Given the rapid pace of urbanisation, urban local governments are facing higher strain on resources and pressure to provide civic infrastructure and service is also rising.

Local governments' capital expenditures, particularly those of larger urban government bodies such as municipal corporations, are considered to have an impact on the welfare and economic growth of cities (Kuntari, 2019; Kuntari et al., 2019). Additionally, municipal corporations have a significant impact on district-

level growth outcomes, and their fiscal operations—such as taxing and spending—have statewide macroeconomic implications (Bandyopadhyay et al., 2024). Numerous research conducted in developing nations have attempted to evaluate the influence of local government fiscal autonomy on regional economic development. Nonetheless, there aren't many studies on the association between municipal fiscal independence and capital expenditure conducted in India, especially Uttar Pradesh which is one of the largest and most populous state. In this paper, we attempt to empirically test the impact of fiscal autonomy of the municipal corporations of Uttar Pradesh on their capital expenditure.

Objective of study

Rest of the paper is structured as: in the next section, we review the extant empirical and theoretical literature related to the issue and briefly describe the research gap, the third section contains detailed explanation of the data and methodological tools and techniques adopted. We report and discuss the empirical results obtained in the fourth section. Finally, the paper concludes with implications of the study and policy suggestions.

Review of Literature

The extant literature on the relationship between municipal fiscal autonomy and capital investments has mixed views. Revenue autonomy is believed to be a significant determinant of expenditure decisions and patterns of the local governments (Nugeraha et al., 2024). Capital expenditures by the municipal governments are important factors that influence the growth of urban infrastructure and services, but the inability of lower tier governments to fund their expenditures through own sources hinder optimum service delivery (Malhotra et al., 2022). Expenditure decentralisation has a greater impact in promoting growth at both local and national levels (Delang & Sitorus, 2024; Ganaie et al., 2018). On the contrary, some of the empirical analysis of higher autonomy and greater decentralisation of fiscal functions of local government institutions suggests there is a negative impact on growth and capital investments at the regional levels of a nation (Lutz, 2015; Sridhar & Ravi, 2022). The studies of Lestari & Basuki (2024), Ningrum et al. (2024) assess the impact of tax, non-tax revenues and economic growth on local capital expenditure in various cities and provinces of Indonesia and found that economic growth highly effects capital expenditure, non-tax revenues are also major determinants of spending of the local governments, whereas tax revenues do not have a significant relationship with expenditure patterns and decisions.

In Indian context, several studies such as Bandyopadhyay et al. (2024), Gandhi & Pethe (2017) Jain & Joshi (2015), and Pethe & Lalvani (2006) reveal that major proportion of municipal expenditure is financed through government transfers and aid obtained by local governments. The over dependence of local governments on higher tier governments seriously affects the assets creation and service provision. More fiscal autonomy is needed in order to facilitate improved service delivery in the urban areas (Gandhi & Pethe, 2017). Municipal governments are key economic agents working at the grassroot level and actively influence urban development outcomes, greater independence of these governments can ensure optimum infrastructure development through capital investments and these investments are greatly determined by decentralisation of revenue and expenditure functions (Jain & Joshi, 2015). Though, a vast literature, both empirical and theoretical is available on the issue of fiscal autonomy of local governments, there are little to none empirical studies on the relationship between fiscal autonomy and capital expenditure which is a major source of urban infrastructure development. This study attempts to fill this research gap by empirically validation the aforementioned relationship.

Methodology

The study uses secondary data for empirical estimation. The panel data of 17 Municipal Corporations[3] of Uttar Pradesh for the period of 2012-13 to 2020-21 has been extracted from the annual reports of Uttar Pradesh Directorate of Economics and Statistics. Main variables of the study include the dependent variable- Capital Expenditure incurred by the Municipal Corporations denoted by *Capex*. The independent variables of the model consist of various indicators of municipal fiscal autonomy and dependence. The ratio of MCs' total revenue to state's total revenue denoted by A1, ratio of MCs' total expenditure to the state's expenditure denoted by A2, ratio of Municipal Corporations' own sourced revenue to total revenue including government transfers denoted by A3, ratio of Municipal Corporations' own revenue to their total expenditure denoted by A4, to appropriately incorporate the size of the Municipal Corporations in the model, we use persons employed in the MCs as one of the independent variables which is denoted by *Emp*. Economic growth at the district level is also a key element in determining the revenue and expenditure decisions of local government institutions therefore we use the Gross District Domestic Products of the respective districts as an control variable. The variables *Capex*, *Y*, and *Emp* are in natural logarithmic form. A detailed description of the variables and the sources are shown in Table1. In order to select the most appropriate model for our dataset we employ several pre and post estimation tests. Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) were calculated to check for multicollinearity which tests how much variance of the estimated coefficients are inflated due to multicollinearity. In order

to detect for autocorrelation in the panel data, we employ Wooldridge test, the results of which are reported in the next section.

To empirically validate the impact of municipal fiscal autonomy and local economic growth on capital expenditure of the MCs, we both Fixed and Random Effects Models and the Hausman test following the model estimations to select the most appropriate model. The models we estimate are specified in equations 1 and 2.

Model Specification

The Fixed Effects Model we estimate can be specified as follows:

$$LnCapex_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 A1_{it} + \beta_2 A2_{it} + \beta_3 A3_{it} + \beta_4 A4_{it} + \beta_5 LnY_{it} + \beta_6 LnEmp_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad \dots 1$$

Where, α_i represents the fixed effects (time-invariant characteristics specific to entity i), ϵ_{it} is the error term and it denotes observation for entity i at time t .

The Random Effects Model we estimate can be specified as follows:

$$LnCapex_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 A1_{it} + \beta_2 A2_{it} + \beta_3 A3_{it} + \beta_4 A4_{it} + \beta_5 LnY_{it} + \beta_6 LnEmp_{it} + \mu_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad \dots 2$$

$LnCapex_{it}$ is the dependent variable for entity i at time t .

α is the intercept.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_6$ are the coefficients for the independent variables.

μ_{it} is the random effect, capturing unobserved heterogeneity across entities (assumed to be $\mu_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_{\mu}^2)$).

ϵ_{it} is the idiosyncratic error term (assumed to be $\epsilon_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_{\epsilon}^2)$).

Analysis

Appendix

Table 1A. Descriptive Statistics

Variable		Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Observations
LnCapex	overall	8.807848	1.038999	5.273	11.08345	N = 135
	between		0.7055747	7.359332	10.31107	n = 17
	within		0.7949457	5.939606	10.63156	T = 7.94
A1	overall	0.0010383	0.0011621	0	0.0059426	N = 153
	between		0.0010136	0.0001319	0.0036867	n = 17
	within		0.0006141	-0.0005837	0.0040415	T = 9
A2	overall	0.0012871	0.0013155	0	0.0075335	N = 153
	between		0.0012315	0.0001054	0.0049559	n = 17
	within		0.0005418	-0.0001956	0.0040257	T = 9
A3	overall	0.3435227	0.2297344	0	0.9714146	N = 153
	between		0.1162011	0.1031646	0.5984153	n = 17
	within		0.1999647	0.0145541	1.033141	T = 9
A4	overall	0.3989737	0.3460378	0	3.07404	N = 153
	between		0.1318199	0.138279	0.6106598	n = 17
	within		0.3213723	-0.0039477	2.862354	T = 9
LnY	overall	14.70651	0.5134381	13.49473	15.71391	N = 153
	between		0.4335693	13.95915	15.31082	n = 17
	within		0.2924554	14.03728	15.19413	T = 9
LnEmp	overall	7.983079	0.6522865	6.391917	9.418492	N = 135
	between		0.69964	6.403896	9.060923	n = 17
	within		0.2432357	7.376022	8.656783	T = 7.94

Table 2A. Pairwise Correlations Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
(1) LnCapex	1.000						
(2) A1	0.435	1.000					
(3) A2	0.606	0.752	1.000				
(4) A3	0.053	0.520	0.222	1.000			
(5) A4	-0.237	0.366	0.037	0.704	1.000		
(6) LnY	0.438	0.558	0.515	0.518	0.377	1.000	
(7) LnEmp	0.543	0.659	0.694	0.074	-0.028	0.559	1.000

Source: Author's own work.

Result and Discussion

Table 1. Description of Variables

Dependent Variable		
<i>LnCapex</i>	Natural Logarithm of Capital Expenditure incurred by the Municipal Corporations.	Data on all variables is extracted from annual reports on local government finance, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Government of Uttar Pradesh.
Independent Variables		
<i>A1</i>	Ratio of total revenue of Municipal Corporations to total revenue of the state.	
<i>A2</i>	Ration of total expenditure of the Municipal Corporations to total Expenditure of the state.	
<i>A3</i>	Ratio of own sourced revenue (tax and non-tax revenues) to total revenue including government transfers and aid of the Municipal Corporations.	
<i>A4</i>	Ratio of own sourced revenue to total expenditure incurred by the Municipal Corporations.	
<i>LnY</i>	Natural Logarithm of Gross District Domestic Product at current prices.	
<i>LnEmp</i>	Natural Logarithm of persons employed in the Municipal Corporations	

Pre-estimation Test Results

Table 2. Description of Variables

Variables	VIF	Wooldridge Test
F Statistic		1.15
P>F		0.29
<i>A1</i>	3.81	
<i>A2</i>	3.19	
<i>A3</i>	2.11	
<i>A4</i>	1.83	
<i>LnY</i>	1.69	
<i>LnEmp</i>	2.61	

The VIF values as reported in Table 2, the values are a measure of degree of multicollinearity among independent variables. We employed a simple pooled OLS as a proxy to employ VIF test. Values for all independent variables are well below the common threshold of 5. This suggests our variables are not severely affected by multicollinearity. A1 and A2 have relatively high VIF values of 3.81 and 3.19 respectively but this does not severely affect our estimation since acceptable VIF values reach up to 10. The Wooldridge test also yields favourable results. The null hypothesis for the test is that there is no first order autocorrelation in the variables. The F statistic of 1.15 with associated p value of 0.29 suggests we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no first order autocorrelation. The absence of autocorrelation means we can proceed with the estimation.

Model Results

The estimated coefficients of fixed effects, random effects models along with the simple pooled OLS model are reported in Table 3. The Hausman test performed yields a chi-square value of 11.39 with a p-value of 0.07. This result suggests that we fail to reject the null hypothesis at the 5% significance level ($p > 0.05$). Thus, there is insufficient evidence to conclude that the fixed effects model is more appropriate than the random effects model. Therefore, for our analysis, we rely on

the estimated coefficients of the Random effects model. The primary findings of our model are- the estimated coefficients of the variables A2, A4, and LnY are significant at 1 per cent level suggesting expenditure independence, financial autonomy and local economic growth are significant determinants of capital expenditure incurred by MCs, while the coefficients of A1 and LnEmp are statistically insignificant.

Table 3: Regression Results

Dependent Variable: LnCapex	Fixed Effects Model	Random Effects Model	Pooled OLS Model
A1	-86.541 [.489]	-63.54 [.569]	-41.06 [.710]
A2	313.86** [.013]	306.83*** [0.001]	306.05*** [.001]
A3	.522 [.356]	.867* [.067]	.89* [.059]
A4	-.90*** [.001]	-.969*** [.000]	-1.00** [.000]
LnY	1.051*** [.000]	.598*** [.003]	.49** [.011]
LnEmp	.335 [.219]	.253 [.145]	.26 [.113]
R ²	-	-	.48
R ² (within)	.27	.25	-
R ² (between)	.75	.80	-
R ² (overall)	.48	.48	-
F	7.13	-	19.85
Prob > F	0.000	-	0.000
Wald χ^2 (df-6)	-	97.74	-
Prob > χ^2	-	0.000	-

The estimated coefficient of the variable A1 which measures the financial independence and the financial contribution of municipal corporations in comparison to the overall state revenue is negative but statistically insignificant given by the p-value of .569, suggesting revenue independence is not a significant determinant of capital expenditure, this result supports the earlier theoretical consensus that revenue independence is not an active element in promoting urban infrastructure growth (Hasanuddin et al., 2021a). The coefficient for A2 which measures the expenditure independence and the proportion of municipal expenditures in state's expenditures is positive (306.83) and statistically significant at the 1 per cent level given the p-value of 0.001. This result is rather interesting and in support with the empirical literature on local government finance that says expenditure independence and autonomy in spending decisions of the local governments are significant determinants of capital expenditure incurred on urban infrastructure development (Brittain, 2002; Church, 1981; Ganaie et al., 2018; Mathur, 2006). Coefficient of A3 that measures Revenue autonomy of the municipal corporations is positive 0.867 and significant the 10 per cent level with the associated p-value of 0.067. This suggests that the revenue autonomy of the municipal corporations is a positive determinant of capital expenditure but the relationship is weak. The studies of (Hasanuddin et al., 2021a; Lestari & Basuki, 2024; Ningrum et al., 2024) found similar evidences. The coefficient for A4 that measures expenditure autonomy of the MCs is negative -0.969 with associated p-value of 0.000, meaning the coefficient is significant at the 1 per cent level. This negative relationship between capital expenditure and spending autonomy is contradictory to the extant literature that says spending autonomy highly impacts capital outlays. The local economic growth as measured by GDDP (LnY) is also significant determinant of the capital outlay given by a coefficient of 0.598 with a p-value of 0.003. The theoretical argument that economic growth at the regional levels significantly determines the growth of infrastructure in cities and urban areas is reinforced by this result (Hasanuddin et al., 2021b; Lestari & Basuki, 2024). Finally, the coefficient for persons employed (LnEmp) is also positive but statistically insignificant shown by the p-value of 0.145 which suggests that number of people employed in the MCs does not have any impact on deciding the quantum of capital expenditure.

Furthermore, the Wald chi-squared statistic of 97.74 with an p-value of 0.000 proves the joint significance of the independent variables of the model. This means the model is appropriate and independent variables are significant in terms of having an influence on the dependent variable LnCapex. The estimated model and the results obtained are robust.

Conclusion

Based on the empirical findings obtained through the model using panel data of 17 municipal corporations of Uttar Pradesh, several conclusions can be drawn. First, the expenditure contribution of the MCs in state's total expenditures need to be augmented in order to boost the growth of urban infrastructure to keep up with the pace of

urbanisation. Revenue autonomy of these large urban government institutions plays a key role in enhancing capital investments so more autonomy should be provided. The revenue collection and taxing capacities of the local governments in India are limited because a majority of the taxes and tax rates are decided by the state governments. Major taxes such as property tax and non-tax revenue sources such as fees and user charges, licensing, etc. are major sources of revenue but inefficiency in tax collection and management hinders the potential increment in generating enough revenue to sustain the local government expenditures on their own. Economic growth at the district level also largely affects the capital expenditure incurred by municipal governments. Thus, more attention and policies oriented towards augmenting growth at the local levels are required. Finally, there is a desperate need to enhance data availability regarding the finances and performance of the local governments in India. Centralised data portals could be established and the local governments should be mandated to maintain transparency and accounting of the relevant data in order to facilitate empirical research which in turn enhances the policy formation process. Rigorous research, both empirical and theoretical is needed in the field of local government finances.

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Endnote

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